

Cycle-Complete Graph Ramsey Numbers

$$r(C_4, K_9), r(C_5, K_8) \leq 33$$

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Abstract For an integer $k \geq 1$, a cycle-complete graph Smarandache-Ramsey number $r_{s^k}(C_m, K_n)$ is the smallest integer N such that every graph G of order N contains k cycles, C_m , on m vertices or the complement of G contains k complete graph, K_n , on n vertices. If $k = 1$, then the Smarandache-Ramsey number $r_{s^k}(C_m, K_n)$ is nothing but the classical Ramsey number $r(C_m, K_n)$. Radziszowski and Tse proved that $r(C_4, K_9) \geq 30$. Also, By considering the known graph $G = 7K_4$, we have that $r(C_5, K_8) \geq 29$. In this paper we give an upper bound of $r(C_4, K_9)$ and $r(C_5, K_8)$.

Key Words: (Smarandache-)Ramsey number; independent set; cycle; complete graph.

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§1. Introduction

Through out this paper we adopt the standard notations, a cycle on m vertices will be denoted by C_m and the complete graph on n vertices by K_n . The minimum degree of a graph G is denoted by $\delta(G)$. An independent set of vertices of a graph G is a subset of $V(G)$ in which no two vertices are adjacent. The independence number of a graph G , $\alpha(G)$, is the size of the largest independent set.

For an integer $k \geq 1$, a Smarandache-Ramsey number $r_{s^k}(H, F)$ is the smallest integer N such that every graph G of order N contains k graph H , or the complement of G contains k graph F . If $k = 1$, then the Smarandache-Ramsey number $r_{s^k}(H, F)$ is nothing but the classical Ramsey number $r(H, F)$. $r(C_m, K_n)$ is called the cycle-complete graph Ramsey number. In one of the earliest contributions to graphical Ramsey theory, Bondy and Erdős [3] proved that for all $m \geq n^2 - 2$, $r(C_m, K_n) = (m - 1)(n - 1) + 1$. The restriction in the above result was improved by Nikiforov [10] when he proved the equality for $m \geq 4n + 2$. Erdős et al. [5] conjectured that $r(C_m, K_n) = (m - 1)(n - 1) + 1$, for all $m \geq n \geq 3$ except $r(C_3, K_3) = 6$. The conjectured were

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confirmed for some $n = 3, 4, 5$ and 6 (see [2], [6], [12], and [14]). Moreover, in [7] and [8] the conjecture was proved for $m = n = 8$, and $m = 8$ with $n = 7$. Also, the case $n = m = 7$ was proved independently by Baniabedalruhman and Jaradat [1] and Cheng et al. [4].

In a related work, Radziszowski and Tse [11] showed that $r(C_4, K_7) = 22$, $r(C_4, K_8) = 26$ and $r(C_4, K_9) \geq 30$. Also, In [8] Jayawardene and Rousseau proved that $r(C_5, K_6) = 21$. Recently, Schiermeyer [13] and Cheng et al. [4] proved that $r(C_5, K_7) = 25$ and $r(C_6, K_7) = 25$, respectively. In this article we prove the following Theorems:

Theorem A *The complete-cycle Ramsey number $r(C_4, K_9) \leq 33$.*

Theorem B *The complete-cycle Ramsey number $r(C_5, K_8) \leq 33$.*

In the rest of this work, $N(u)$ stands for the neighbor of the vertex u which is the set of all vertices of G that are adjacent to u and $N[u] = N(u) \cup \{u\}$. For a subgraph R of the graph G and $U \subseteq V(G)$, $N_R(U)$ is defined as $(\cup_{u \in U} N(u)) \cap V(R)$. Finally, $\langle V_1 \rangle_G$ stands for the subgraph of G whose vertex set is $V_1 \subseteq V(G)$ and whose edge set is the set of those edges of G that have both ends in V_1 and is called the subgraph of G induced by V_1 .

§2. Proof of Theorem A

We prove our result using the contradiction. Suppose that G is a graph of order 33 which contains neither C_4 nor a 9-element independent set. Then we have the following:

1. $\delta(G) \geq 7$. Assume that u is a vertex with $d(u) \leq 6$. Then $|V(G) - N[u]| \geq 33 - 7 = 26$. But $r(C_4, K_8) = 26$. Hence, $G - N[u]$ contains an 8-element independent set. This set with u form a 9-element independent set. That is a contradiction.

2. G contains no K_3 . Suppose that G contains K_3 . Let $\{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$ be the vertex set of K_3 . Also, let $R = G - \{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$ and $U_i = N(u_i) \cap V(R)$. Then $U_i \cap U_j = \emptyset$ because otherwise G contains C_4 . Also, for each $x \in U_i$ and $y \in U_i$, we have that $xy \notin E(G)$ because otherwise G contains C_4 . Now, since $\delta(G) \geq 7$, $|U_i| \geq 5$. Since $r(P_3, K_3) = 5$, as a result either $\langle U_i \rangle_G$ contains P_3 for some $i = 1, 2, 3$ and so G contains C_4 or $\langle U_i \rangle_G$ does not contains P_3 for each $i = 1, 2, 3$ and so each of which contains a 3-element independent set, Thus, three independent set of each consists a 9-element independent set. This is a contradiction.

Now, let u be a vertex of G . Let $N(u) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_r\}$ where $r \geq 7$. Since G contains no K_3 , as a result $\langle N(u) \cup \{u\} \rangle_G$ forms a star. And so, $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_r\}$ is independent. Now, let $N(u_1) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k, u\}$ where $k \geq 6$. For the same reasons, $\langle N(u_1) \cup \{u_1\} \rangle_G$ forms a star and so $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}$ is independent. Since G contains no K_3 and no C_4 . Then $\{u_2, \dots, u_r, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}$ is an independent set. That is a contradiction. The proof is complete. \square

§3. Proof of Theorem B

We prove our result by using the contradiction. Assume that G is a graph of order 33 which

contains neither C_5 nor an 8-element independent set. By an argument similar to the one in Theorem A and by noting that $r(C_5, K_8) = 25$, we can show that $\delta(G) \geq 8$. Now, we have the following:

1. G contains K_3 . Suppose that G does not contain K_3 . Let $u \in V(G)$ and $r = |N(u)|$. Then the induced subgraph $\langle N(u) \rangle_G$ does not contain P_2 . Hence $\langle N(u) \rangle_G$ is a null graph with r vertices. Since $\alpha(G) \leq 7$, as a result $r \leq 7$. Therefore, $8 \leq \delta(G) \leq r \leq 7$. That is a contradiction.

2. G contains $K_4 - e$. Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$ be the vertex set of K_3 . Let $R = G - U$ and $U_i = N(u_i) \cap V(R)$ for each $1 \leq i \leq 3$. Since $\delta(G) \geq 8$, $|U_i| \geq 6$ for all $1 \leq i \leq 3$. Now we have the following two cases:

Case 1: $U_i \cap U_j \neq \emptyset$ for some $1 \leq i < j \leq 3$, say $w \in U_i \cap U_j$. Then it is clear that G contains $K_4 - e$. In fact, the induced subgraph $\langle U \cup \{w\} \rangle_G$ contains $K_4 - e$.

Case 2 : $U_i \cap U_j = \emptyset$ for each $1 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Then $\alpha(\langle U_i \rangle_G) \leq 2$, for some $1 \leq i \leq 3$. To see that suppose that $\alpha(\langle U_i \rangle_G) \geq 3$ for each $1 \leq i \leq 3$. Since between any two vertices of U there is a path of order 3, as a result for any $x \in U_i$ and $y \in U_j$, we have $xy \notin E(G)$, $1 \leq i < j \leq 3$ because otherwise G contains C_5 . Therefore, $\alpha(\langle U_1 \cup U_2 \cup U_3 \rangle_G) \geq 3 + 3 + 3 = 9$. and so $\alpha(G) \geq 9$, which is a contradiction.

Now, since $|U_i| \geq 6$ and $\alpha(\langle U_i \rangle_G) \leq 2$, for some $1 \leq i \leq 3$ and since $r(K_3, K_3) = 6$ as a result the induced subgraph $\langle U_i \rangle_G$ contains K_3 . And so $\langle U_i \cup \{u_i\} \rangle_G$ contains K_4 . Hence, G contains $K_4 - e$.

3. G contains K_4 . Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ be the vertex set of $K_4 - e$, where the induced subgraph of $\{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$ is isomorphic to K_3 . Without loss of generality we may assume that $u_1u_4, u_2u_4 \in E(G)$. We consider the case where $u_3u_4 \notin E(G)$ because otherwise the result is obtained. Let $R = G - U$ and $U_i = N(u_i) \cap V(R)$ for each $1 \leq i \leq 4$. Then as in **2**, $|U_i| \geq 5$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $|U_i| \geq 6$ for $i = 3, 4$. To this end, we have that $U_i \cap U_j = \emptyset$ for all $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ except possibly for $i = 1$ and $j = 2$ (To see that suppose that $w \in U_i \cap U_j$ for some $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ with $i \neq 1$ or $j \neq 2$. Then we consider the following cases:

- (1) $i = 3$ and $j = 4$. Then $u_3wu_4u_1u_2u_3$ is a cycle of order 5, a contradiction.
- (2) $i = 3$ and $j = 2$. Then $u_3wu_2u_4u_1u_3$ is a cycle of order 5, a contradiction.
- (3) i, j are not as in the above cases. Then by similar argument as in (2) G contains a C_5 .

This is a contradiction.

Now, By arguing as in Case 2 of 2, $\alpha(\langle U_2 \rangle_G) \leq 1$ or $\alpha(\langle U_i \rangle_G) \leq 2$, for $i = 3$ or 4 . And so, the induced subgraph $\langle U_i \rangle_G$ contains K_3 for some $2 \leq i \leq 4$. Thus, G contains K_4 .

To this end, let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ be the vertex set of K_4 . Let $R = G - U$ and $U_i = N(u_i) \cap V(R)$ for each $1 \leq i \leq 4$. Since $\delta(G) \geq 8$, $|U_i| \geq 5$ for all $1 \leq i \leq 4$. Since there is a path of order 4 joining any two vertices of U , as a result $U_i \cap U_j = \emptyset$ for all $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ (since otherwise, if $w \in U_i \cap U_j$ for some $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$, then the concatenation of the u_i - u_j path of order 4 with u_iwu_j is a cycle of order 5, a contradiction). Similarly, since there is a path of order 3 joining any two vertices of U , as a result for all $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ and for all $x \in U_i$ and $y \in U_j$, $xy \notin E(G)$ (otherwise, if there are $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ such that $x \in U_i$ and $y \in U_j$, and $xy \in E(G)$, then the concatenation of the u_i - u_j path of order 3 with u_ixyu_j is a cycle of

order 5, a contradiction). Also, since there is a path of order 2 joining any two vertices of U , as a result $N_R(U_i) \cap N_R(U_j) = \emptyset, 1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ (otherwise, if there are $1 \leq i < j \leq 4$ such that $w \in N_R(U_i) \cap N_R(U_j)$, then the concatenation of the u_i - u_j path of order 2 with $u_i x w y u_j$ where $x \in U_i$ and $y \in U_j$, and $xw, yw \in E(G)$ is a cycle of order 5, a contradiction). Therefore, $|U_i \cup N_R(U_i) \cup \{u_i\}| \geq \delta(G) + 1$. Thus, $|V(G)| \geq 4(\delta(G) + 1) \geq 4(8 + 1) = 4 \cdot 9 = 36$. That contradicts the fact that the order of G is 33. \square

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